

FULL PAPER

A multi-site language study on children-robot dialogues

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ABSTRACT

Child-robot interaction (CRI) has been mostly studied in labs and classroom settings. In this work, we share a CRI language processing study carried out in children's homes, analysing how each language processing layer performs with children at home with no researcher present. We carried out an experiment in two phases: a first iteration with 7 families in Spain cohabiting with a simulated robot for 2 weeks and a second iteration with 28 families: 11 in Spain, 9 in Ukraine and 8 in the USA completing 4 cohabitation weeks at each country. The total number of children involved in the experiments was 51, ranging from 5 to 13 years old. Our goal in this study is to evaluate the performance of voice recognition, language understanding and dialogue management when children interact with a robot at home. Our results indicate that dialogue management capabilities are becoming the key element in the language processing pipeline; they also denote that the dialogue engine should include mixed-initiative capabilities and show the relative usage of different common built-in intents.

KEYWORDS

child-robot interaction; natural language processing; dialogue management; cross-cultural study.

1. Introduction

The field of natural language processing (NLP) has made tremendous progress in areas spanning from speech recognition and language understanding to dialogue management. However, there are some barriers that make those tasks particularly challenging within a children's context. In speech recognition, multiple factors make children's voices inherently difficult to process, from the physical features derived from their smaller vocal tracts to their variable usage of grammar and language as they grow up and learn, as described by Potaminos, Narayanan, and Lee [1], and Russell and D'Arcy [2]. Besides these unavoidable limiting factors, the scarcity of public, children-specific, and large datasets makes the development of speech recognition solutions even more

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challenging and usually tackled only by large corporations, as in Liao *et al.*'s (Google) work [3]. Linguistically, understanding children's intents¹ is also more challenging than doing so with adults'. As pointed out by Gray *et al.* [4], "*Children are also more likely to use imaginative words, ungrammatical phrases, incorrect pronunciations, and be interested in different genres than adults, presenting challenges for language modeling*". However, children are very interested in interacting with robots which understand them [5], elevating the urgency for improving the accuracy and reliability of NLP systems for children.

We bring this challenging issue to the forefront in an even more unpredictable and under-studied user setting: children's homes. In a survey of longitudinal studies in human-robot interaction (HRI) published in 2013, of 24 longitudinal studies, only 5 occurred in home environments, but only one was related to a child-centered robot [6]. In that paper, 6 families engaged with a dinosaur robot Pleo for 2 to 10 months with limited engagement after the novelty of the robot wore off [7]. Likewise, in van Straten, Peter and Kühne's [8] review of papers published between 2000 and 2017, the authors could only find one study taking place in children's homes. Additionally, only more recently have researchers focused on this venue for longer periods of time. Zhao and McEwen [9], Michaelis *et al.* [10,11] and Cagiltay *et al.* [12] described experiments that investigated the usage of robots as reading companions. In [9], children used commercial robots at home for 180 days, [10]'s experiment lasted 2 weeks and [11] and [12], 4 weeks. De Jong *et al.* described in [13] an experiment that lasted 8 weeks whose research focus was the acceptance of the robot and how it evolved over the course of the experiment.

Notice that the limited number of child-robot interaction (CRI) studies carried out at children's homes contrasts with the ample set of works found for non-embodied (i.e., non robots) conversational agents (CAs). Garg *et al.*'s [14] survey of CAs papers reported up to 13 works whose focus were precisely the home and family context. While most of those works focus on design and usability, some of them analyse different aspects of the language processing pipeline. Beneteau *et al.* [15], studied communication breakdowns with an Alexa device and described several repair strategies used by children and families. Xu and Warschauer [16] provided a detailed performance analysis of the language processing pipeline for a joint reading scenario. The same authors shared in Xu and Warschauer [17] an experiment where they explored children's responses to open-ended questions and suggested assigning multiple intents to the possible responses to maximize the specificity of the system's feedback. In Monarca *et al.* [18], researchers demonstrated that the communication design in terms of response time thresholds should be adapted to the children's language abilities.

Our work builds on top of these previous studies, analysing the language processing performance when children interact with a robot in children's homes. We carried out the first iteration of the experiment in Spain, lasting 2 weeks with 7 families and 14 children, whose results were published in 2023 [19]. Now we are presenting an extension of that experiment with another iteration carried out in 3 countries (Spain, USA, and Ukraine) with 28 families and 37 children, as detailed in section 3. During both iterations, we used Haru4Kids (H4K), an app-based robot presented in section 2.1, whose language processing module is detailed in section 2.2. We included a set of activities with different degrees of interactivity, the description of which can be found in 3.3.

¹In NLP "intent" is referred to as the categorization of the user's intention for one conversation turn (see <https://cloud.google.com/dialogflow/es/docs/intents-overview>).

Figure 1. *Haru4Kids*: (a) iPad supported by rotating-tabletop stand, and (b) high-level technical description of the system.

In this work we analyse the relative performance of each layer on the language processing pipeline, a critical component for successful child-robot interaction. As part of this analysis, we investigate what type of dialogue strategy is more appreciated by the user (user-driven vs system-driven vs mixed-initiative) and we evaluate the usage of different common built-in intents across 3 countries with 3 different languages. The results of the study are detailed in section 4, and the contributions derived from those results are summarized in section 6.

2. Haru4Kids (H4K)

2.1. Platform and Software Architecture

The H4K platform simulates the Haru robot [20] and its capabilities on a tablet PC. The main motivation to create this platform was to minimize the risks inherent to hardware deployment at children’s homes, as explained in section 3.4.

H4K consists of a Haru avatar displayed on an iPad supported by a rotating stand (Fig.1a). This rotating stand is connected to the app’s computer vision component which enables the iPad’s camera to identify where children are and orient towards them. To do this, it utilizes two degrees of freedom: roll and yaw angles.

The app is designed to work on the iPad and uses several *Apple*-specific libraries. At the highest level of abstraction, the application is divided into seven main modules: User Interface, Conversation Manager, Vision Manager, Central Controller, Settings Manager, Logging, and Stand Manager (Fig.1b). The Central Controller acts as the coordinator of the app’s behavior, interacting with other modules and accessing the *cloud* as needed.

The main difference in terms of user experience between the first and second iterations of the experiment is that, for the second experiment, we added an initial login screen that let us know which child was using H4K in every session. There was also an option to adjust content based on academic grade level.

2.2. Conversation Manager

The Conversation Manager handles the components needed for voice-based interactions. For speech recognition and synthesis, the Conversation Manager makes use of

Apple’s built-in libraries and its default configuration and models for Spanish: no domain-specific fine-tuning was done. On the other hand, dialogue management did require a custom development. Currently, there is no suitable commercial solution that provides the capabilities required for the kind of interactions offered by the physical Haru prototype [21]. Specifically, in commercial applications, system-initiated sub-dialogues are usually not available or limited to simple question-response short interactions typical of chatbot applications.

H4K’s Conversation Manager makes use of DialogFlow’s [22] intent identification and entity extraction module (*i.e.*, as the Natural Language Understanding -NLU-layer). However, in order to allow for full-fledged mixed-initiative conversations, dialogue management is performed by a custom-developed dialogue container hosted in Amazon Web Services (AWS) that substitutes and expands the dialogue capabilities provided by Dialogflow.

Besides providing mixed-initiative capabilities, H4K’s Dialogue Container brings other advantages. First, it includes a clear separation between back-end logic and dialogue configuration. Second, in this module, we added some domain-independent dialogue capabilities that are particularly useful for error-prone scenarios like ours in the wild. Specifically:

- **Repeat:** Users could ask H4K at anytime to repeat its last utterance.
- **Help:** Users could ask for help. Content creators could also define context-sensitive responses across ‘help’ inquiries.
- **Background:** This mechanism gets triggered in mixed-initiative dialogues when there is neither a system-driven proactive utterance nor a user-driven request. Typically, it would trigger a prompt like “*Is there anything else I can do for you?*”.
- **Sleep:** This built-in intent allows the user to pause the app at any time, sending the robot to sleep. This intent would be triggered by user inputs like “*Go to sleep*” or “*Pause*”.

3. Experiments

3.1. Participants and setup

The experiment had two iterations. In the first iteration, H4K engaged for 2 weeks with 7 families, all in Spain. The results of this iteration included an analysis of the pre and post interviews [5], a report on the user’s engagement with the robot [23] and a first language study [19] that served as the basis for this work.

In this second iteration, the experiment was enlarged in multiple dimensions, including geographically (from 1 to 3 countries) and in terms of sample size (from 7 to 28 families) and time of cohabitation (from 2 to 4 weeks).

Overall, the experiment took place in 3 countries: Spain (both iterations), USA (second iteration), and Ukraine (second iteration). All participants were native speakers (Spanish, English and Ukrainian). We used convenience recruitment, making use of researchers’ contacts and word of mouth, seeking families with children in between 5 and 13 years old.

Table 1 details the experiment’s general information per country.

As pointed out by [24], this kind of exploratory study is typically performed with smaller sample sizes than the ones in experimental research. Actually, our experiments include a significantly larger sample size than other long-term exploratory CRI studies

Table 1. Items per activity and country

	Families	Children	Male	Min Age	Max Age	Avg Age
Spain (1st iteration)	7	14	9	6	13	9,6
Spain (2nd iteration)	11	16	11	5	11	8,2
USA	8	9	6	7	11	8,3
Ukraine	9	12	5	6	12	8,6
TOTAL	35	51	31	5	13	8,7

such as the ones carried out by Leyzberg et. al [25], with N = 19 children, by Kory-Westlund and Breazeal [26], with N=14 children, or by [12], also with N=14 children.

Researchers went to each family’s home, and after informing them in detail about the experiment, gathered their participation agreement forms, set-up the system, and explained to the parents how to configure the level of information sharing. Then, the researchers gave a brief introduction on how to use the platform to all family members. In the first iteration of experiments, researchers left children to explore H4K’s characteristics and features on their own. In particular, no details were given in terms of dialogue capabilities: no reference to mixed-initiative support and no explanation about the *Repeat* or *Help* intents described in section 2.1. However, for this second iteration, following the conclusions of the first iteration, researchers did explain these capabilities to the children, including specific examples.

Participants interacted with the system through the tablet’s microphone and speakers. That is, no external headset or earphone was used to improve the interaction.

3.2. Data collection

All the events occurring during the execution of the application were logged in real-time, both locally on the tablet and on the cloud (by *Cloudwatch* –CW, from *AWS Cloud* [27]). These logs gathered all relevant information for our CRI study, including the speech recognition outcomes, the intents recognized by the NLU component, the ongoing activity, and the initiator of subdialogue (user-driven vs system-driven).

Two surveys were conducted with parents and kids, one before and another one after the cohabitation. The analysis of the insights derived from those surveys in the first iteration of the experiment (only Spain) were reported in [5].

3.3. H4K activities

By default, H4K was in sleeping mode. Children could wake it up by clicking on a “*wake up*” button, as shown in figure 2. In the second iteration of the experiment, after clicking the “*wake up*” button, the child was asked to identify themselves by choosing among a set of predefined names (one per child in the family) or an alternative “*guest*” option.

Once waken up, H4K would initiate a short small-talk conversation after which it would proactively suggest one of the pre-configured entertainment-educative activities. The activities were designed under the supervision of a neuro-psychologist with the main objective of stimulating children’s brains. There was a variety of activities, in order to target different cognitive functions and capabilities, such as attention, memory, language, reasoning, comprehension, perception and processing speed. In the first

Figure 2. Child waking up H4K

iteration of the experiment, H4K included the activities described in the following list:

- **Storytelling:** H4K tells a story while displaying specific illustrations on the screen, asking occasionally some questions about the story.
- **Crazy Worms:** H4K asks the user to suggest words within different word categories. After compiling a list of words, H4K fills them in blanks of an incomplete story and tells the -usually humorous- resulting story.
- **Detective:** A list of words is given and children need to identify the one word that does not match; for example: “apple, *chair*, banana, peach”.
- **Would you rather ...?:** H4K presents two silly options from which the user has to choose one; *e.g.*, “Would you rather have three eyes or two noses?”.
- **Jokes:** H4K tells three child-friendly jokes in a row.

For the second iteration, the list was enlarged with the following set of activities:

- **Alphabet Game:** H4K asked one question per letter in the alphabet, the answer starting by each one of the letters. The goal of the child is to answer all questions right.
- **Number Guessing:** The child must find out the number that H4K has randomly chosen. For every incorrect attempt, H4K answers either “higher” or “lower”. There were 3 instances of this game, depending on the range: 0-10, 0-100 and 0-1000.
- **20 questions:** The child chooses a food or an animal and H4K must figure it out by asking at most 20 yes/no questions.
- **True/False:** H4K shares a statement and the child must say if that statement is true or false.
- **Right Option:** H4K asks a question and provides a set of possible answers. The child must tell which is the valid one.
- **Riddles:** H4K tells a popular riddle and the child must answer.
- **Tongue Twisters:** H4K says a tongue twister and the child must repeat it properly.

The number of actual instances per activity and country varied based on the material available per language for the content creators. For instance, there were many Tongue Twisters in Ukraine and the USA compared to Spain, but many more Detective Games in Spain compared to Ukraine or the USA. Table 2 reports the items used for the experiment in each country.

Table 2. Items per activity and country

	Spain	Ukraine	USA
Alphabet Game	79	6	18
Detective	154	35	35
Jokes	33	70	57
Crazy Worm	6	0	0
Number Guessing	3	3	3
Riddles	20	43	33
Right Option	18	18	18
Stories	12	9	11
Tongue Twister	38	180	126
True/False	72	118	48
20 questions	2	2	2
Would you rather	9	9	70

This selection of activities was diverse in terms of interactivity, with *Jokes* and *Storytelling* being mostly passive, whereas the other ones required active participation from the users. The activities were also variable in terms of duration, from the short *Would you rather?* and *Jokes* to the longer *Storytelling*.

In our experiment, we sought to evaluate how language processing accuracy may change depending on the type of question and activity. With that goal in mind, we classified all system driven-questions depending on the expected answer: yes/no, multiple choice, and open/ended questions.

3.4. Ethical Aspects

An Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval was obtained prior to starting cohabitation in both iterations. Caregivers provided consent and children aged 7 or older provided written assent. The IRB clearance request took into special consideration the situation of Ukrainian families, who were suffering the war while the cohabitation was taking place. Researchers underlined the option of dropping out of the study at any given time without advance notice. They were also asked to stop interacting with and leave the robot hardware behind in case they needed to seek shelter due to air raid alarms or other dangers. To minimize the physical risks for all participants, all hardware deployed (both tablets and stands) were commercial solutions easily found on the market and largely used for other purposes.

Families were informed that they could opt-in for image and audio recording during their usage of H4K, but by default both image and audio options were deactivated. They were also informed that, even if they opted-in, no image or audio would ever be uploaded to the cloud and all media would be saved locally on the device. Only researchers included in the IRB clearance were allowed afterwards to access those images and audio recordings for research purposes. To avoid excessive usage, parents could configure H4K settings adapting the allowed usage time. By default, the system had

no restrictions, but parents were instructed how to modify that option if they wanted to. H4K settings include a field that lets families configure the age of the youngest kid at home. The activities were classified with the minimum appropriate age, so no content designed for older children was provided to younger ones. As compensation for their time, parents were given a gift-card for a popular online store and children were given some stickers.

4. Results

H4K was used for a total of 83:11 hours (18:22 hours in the first iteration, 64:49 hours in the second), split into 1,309 sessions with at least one interaction among all families.

Only one family limited their usage time to afternoon-only; the rest of the parents made H4K available 24/7. All families except for 3 (all of them in Spain) opted-in for audio recording, so we collected 12,303 recorded prompts from a total of 13,847 prompts registered throughout the experiment.

The following sections describe the results obtained at different levels: speech recognition, language understanding, and dialogue management.

4.1. Children’s speech recognition in the wild

All recorded prompts were transcribed by native speakers, and then the Word Error Rate (WER) was calculated. The WER for the second iteration of experiments was 0.179 for English, 0.171 for Spanish and 0.161 for Ukrainian, significantly worse than the 0.077 reported in the first iteration of experiments. Since the hardware and setup was identical in both iterations, it seems that the significant growth in content had a direct negative effect on the speech recognition accuracy. A remarkable observation is the very similar WER among languages, despite including the relatively low-resourced Ukrainian. In fact, Ukrainian shows a slightly better WER than English and Spanish.

The WER per question type is depicted in Table 3. In the table, column “multiple” groups together all possible answers to all multiple choice questions and “open” does it for open-ended questions; “activity” refers to all user-driven inputs requesting to start a particular activity.

As expected, answers to yes/no questions had better WER than multiple-choice ones, and open-ended questions got the worst WER. The table also includes WER for the built-in intents, where the low performance of “help” in USA and Ukraine is probably due to poor training datasets of those particular classifiers.

Table 3. WER per question type

	yes/no	multiple	open	sleep	repeat	help	activity
Spain	0.081	0.173	0.187	0.149	0.083	0.169	0.154
Ukraine	0.080	0.187	0.199	0.000	0.363	0.730	0.220
USA	0.174	0.145	0.271	0.000	0.042	0.748	0.212
All (average)	0.093	0.168	0.201	0.123	0.127	0.240	0.163

The detailed results classified by activity and country are depicted in Table 4. A clear outlier is the low performance of the True/False activity in USA, due to very frequent missrecognitions of the word “False” (frequently recognized as “Falls”). Another interesting observation is the difference among activities for the different

languages (e.g., very bad for tongue twister in Spanish but acceptable in English, and the other way around for riddles), which is probably just a consequence of the difference in relative complexity of the particular activities chosen for each language.

Table 4. Items per activity and country

	Spain	Ukraine	USA
Alphabet Game	0.197	0.244	0.195
Detective	0.248	0.248	0.207
Small talk	0.176	0.193	0.110
Crazy Worms	0.132	N/A	N/A
Number Guessing	0.168	0.112	0.305
Riddles	0.192	0.253	0.400
Right Option	0.193	0.134	0.165
Stories	0.178	0.207	0.162
Tongue Twister	0.367	0.310	0.097
True/False	0.108	0.114	0.511
20 questions	0.075	0.063	0.073
Would you rather	0.100	0.213	0.119

4.2. Children’s language understanding in the wild

Tables 5 (iteration 1, only Spain) and 6 (iteration 2, all 3 countries) show the intent recognition performance for the main intents of the application, grouped by “intent-type” and applying the usual metrics: precision, recall and F1-score. We also included F ($\beta = 0.5$) since false positives are usually more harmful than false negatives in this context. For computing the different metrics while grouping categories, we used micro-average to smooth the impact of underrepresented classes (like the intent *Repeat*) on the total figures.

In table 5 (first iteration, only Spain), *Help* is not included because that intent was triggered very few times and only by families that didn’t opt-in for audio recording.

Table 5. Intent Recognition Performance - Iteration 1 (only Spain)

	yes/no	multiple	sleep	repeat	activity
Precision	0.992	0.985	1.000	1.000	0.993
Recall	0.985	0.958	0.886	1.000	0.987
F ($\beta = 1$)	0.989	0.971	0.939	1.00	0.990
F ($\beta = 0.5$)	0.991	0.980	0.975	1.00	0.992

In table 6 (second iteration, all 3 countries), *Help* is included as well as a new *open* “intent-type” since in the second iteration there were activities that included open-ended questions.

The results shown in these tables describe a robust NLU layer within activities, with F ($\beta = 0.5$) above 0.95 for all yes/no, multiple-choice, and open-ended question types. Interestingly, the relative difference in terms of WER between these categories does not translate into differences at NLU level, where the F ($\beta = 0.5$) scores are very similar.

However, the results are worse when it comes to user inputs out of the individual

Table 6. Intent Recognition Performance - Iteration 2 (all 3 countries)

	yes/no	multiple	open	sleep	repeat	help	activity
Precision	0.962	0.977	0.981	0.956	0.824	0.766	0.828
Recall	0.959	0.944	0.953	0.858	0.857	0.867	0.849
F ($\beta = 1$)	0.960	0.960	0.967	0.905	0.840	0.814	0.838
F ($\beta = 0.5$)	0.962	0.970	0.976	0.935	0.830	0.784	0.832

activities, like sleep, help, repeat, or asking to trigger a different activity, all below F ($\beta = 0.5$) 0.90. A per-country analysis confirms that these observations apply to all 3 languages.

These general conclusions, however, have to be qualified by the fact that this analysis does not account for special situations unrelated to predefined intents. Specifically, it does not consider:

- **Recognition Errors:** Inputs where the automatic speech recognition (ASR) engine was not able to provide any transcription above its internal confidence threshold.
- **Silences:** Situations in which the ASR did not capture anything within the predefined time-frame (3.5 seconds), or when the user did not say anything (which is not an ASR error).
- **Out Of Scope (OOS):** The input could not be matched to any of the predefined intents. In some cases, this was the expected behaviour: the open-ended questions were put in place to check the ASR performance, with no intention to process the input.

These three cases happened very often. Figure 3 shows the distribution of these situations depending on the question type for all 3 countries combined, with very similar results for each country. In the diagram, “expected” applies to responses that matched the question type (*e.g.*, “yes” or “no” for a yes/no question) and “other” refers to a valid in-domain intent other than the expected response (*e.g.*, the user asking for help, or requesting to launch another activity).

The more directed the question, the higher the percentage of “expected” responses, ranging from the 93,4% for simple yes/no questions to 53,9% when the questions were open-ended.

Accurately identifying and handling OOS inputs is critical for the user experience [28]. Some commercial NLU systems, including Dialogflow’s, come with a “fallback” built-in intent that captures these kinds of inputs. The performance analysis of this intent also showed a robust behaviour with $F(\beta = 0.5)=0.916$ in the first iteration and $F(\beta = 0.5)=0.939$ in the second (above 0.91 in all 3 countries).

As part of the performance analysis, we also checked whether the number of errors were increasing or decreasing as the experiment went on. Figure 4 shows the percentage of recognition errors plus unexpected OOS inputs (*i.e.*, not valid responses to open-ended questions) over the total number of inputs. The percentage remains approximately constant at around 10%, both for the first (only Spain, figure 4a) and the second (three countries combined, figure 4b) iterations of experiments.

The situation is, however, different when we focus on silence. Figures 5a (first iteration) and 5b (second iteration, all countries combined) show the percentage of inputs “silence” out of the total number of inputs, with a moving average of 3 days to smooth the different usage in different days. These graphs show how the average number of

Figure 3. *Response distribution:* (a) yes/no questions, (b) multiple-choice questions and (c) open-ended questions.

silent inputs decreased in both iterations of the study over time.

4.3. *Child-robot dialogue management in the wild*

Typical dialogue evaluation frameworks like PARADISE [29], include objective usage metrics such as number of turns and dialogue duration. In this second iteration of the experiment, the average number of user turns per session was 11.189, excluding those sessions with zero interactions. Figure 6 details the number of sessions grouped by the number of user turns, showing up to 284 sessions (33% of the total number of dialogues) where children interacted at least 11 times before finishing the session. This is a very significant growth compared to the first iteration of the experiment, where the average number of turns per non-empty session was 6.18%.

Regarding the duration of the sessions, the average time also increased significantly from the average 2:13 minutes in the first iteration of the experiment to 4:57 minutes in the second iteration (excluding zero-turn sessions). The longest average usage happened in Ukraine with 6 minutes and 15 seconds, whereas Spain (4:34 minutes) and USA (4:04 minutes) had shorter average sessions duration.

Besides these standard metrics, we explored the usage of system-driven vs user-driven interactions and the domain-independent dialogue intents that were included in H4K.

As explained previously, H4K’s dialogue management provides mixed-initiative capabilities. Interactions always started in system-driven mode: H4K would initiate a short small-talk interaction after which it would suggest one of the activities at ran-

(a) 1st iteration

(b) 2nd Iteration

Figure 4. Error percentage per day

dom. At any time, users could take control and proactively request one particular activity.

Figure 7 shows the ratio of “user requested” vs “system initiated” per activity in the second iteration of the experiment, showing a similar pattern compared to the one reported in the first iteration. What was different in this second iteration was the evolution of this ratio: in the first iteration, we reported a shift from system-initiated to user-requested [19], whereas in the second iteration, this ratio remained flat for all 3 countries.

The usage of the domain-independent capabilities described in section 2.1 was irregular. As shown in Table 7, the intents *Repeat* and *Help* were used very few times (only 8 combining both intents) in the first iteration of the experiment. In the second iteration of the experiment, these figures remained low for USA and Ukraine, but increased very significantly in Spain. This is coherent with the fact that researchers in Spain were instructed to explicitly explain these conversational capabilities, as a lesson learned from the first iteration. A per-family analysis showed that the built-in intents were evenly used across all homes, confirming that it was an impact of the

(a) 1st iteration

(b) 2nd Iteration

Figure 5. Silence inputs percentage per day

general protocol, not an isolated discovery from one particular family.

5. Discussion

This work aimed to provide insights on child-robot interaction happening in the child’s home, specifically in the area of language processing. We explored the limitations of current solutions at voice recognition, language understanding, and dialogue management levels and tried to identify the best strategies to optimize the interaction.

5.1. Speech Recognition

Voice recognition showed good results despite the very challenging conditions: children as users, recognition in the wild with frequent background noise, distant microphones,

Figure 6. Sessions per number of user turns

Table 7. Usage of Built-in Intents

	sleep	repeat	help	background
Spain (1st iteration)	86	5	3	679
Spain (2nd iteration)	101	70	71	632
Ukraine	8	19	10	362
USA	13	4	2	266

and non-English language. WER was below 0.07 for both yes/no and multiple choice questions, increasing to 0.11 for open-ended questions. These WER figures could probably be further improved by changing and fine-tuning the ASR models to this domain or by applying simple heuristics to cope with the most frequent errors (like "false" vs "falls" in USA).

An unexpected result was the almost identical performance in WER of Ukrainian compared to English and Spanish, actually showing slightly better results. Even in challenging tasks like the tongue twisters or riddles, with plenty of disfluencies, hesitations, and errors, the WER results were very similar.

In a 2009 paper [30], the authors stated that "Typically, the most error-prone component of a spoken dialogue system is speech recognition" and designed their experiments to overcome this limitation and work only with perfect input recognition. Our results indicate that this statement might not be accurate anymore, even for relatively low-resourced languages like Ukrainian, at least for a setup and context like the one described in our experiments. In fact, our results are aligned with the improvements reported at speech recognition level in recent years [31], although not quite yet at the human and even super-human performance levels reported in some public claims.

Figure 7. Proportion of user- versus system-initiated activities

5.2. Language understanding

The natural language understanding (NLU) layer also presented good performance both for in-scope intent recognition and for out-of-scope fallback triggering. The main pre-defined intents got F ($\beta = 0.5$) above 0.95 in both iterations of the experiment, showing therefore a very reliable performance. In general terms, yes/no and multiple choice questions worked smoothly and the issues at the voice recognition level were frequently mitigated by the NLU layer, getting the right semantic interpretation of the children’s input.

When we reported the results of the first iteration of the experiment [19], we hypothesised that 10% of understanding errors might be a hard limit for this kind of application. Now, the detailed analysis of a much larger experiment showed errors again in around 10% of the inputs in all 3 countries, confirming the initial prediction from that paper.

5.3. Dialogue management

At the dialogue level, mixed-initiative capabilities proved very useful. Users often let Haru suggest activities, but also took the initiative, very frequently requesting the activities they were interested in. In the first iteration of the experiment, we observed how system-driven interactions were predominant in the first days of the experiment, shifting smoothly towards user-driven requests in the last days. This shifting did not happen in the second iteration. We believe that this is explained by the different protocols followed in the experiment setup: in the first iteration, researchers left users to discover the activities by themselves (thus needing Haru to suggest an activity before they even knew it existed), whereas in the second iteration, researchers provided a detailed account of the activities available and even showed examples of each activity.

In the first iteration of the experiment, the usage of *Help* and *Repeat* built-in intents was lower than we expected. Most children did not use these capabilities even once. In [19] we speculated that children probably did not even think they could do it and recommended developers to explicitly add an explanation of the conversational

capabilities available to the deployment protocol. Now, in the second iteration of the experiment, we followed our own recommendation and observed a much higher occurrence of both intents.

5.4. Limitations and Future Work

The findings of this study must be limited to and understood under the context in which the experiment was carried out. H4K’s activities were limited to the 12 activities described in section 2.1 and the interactions under study were divided into three basic categories: yes/no vs multiple choice vs open-ended questions. The experiments were also limited in terms of languages (Spanish, English, and Ukrainian) and geographical location (Spain, USA, and Ukraine).

Besides this language study, this cross-cultural experiment has provided much information in terms of user preferences, usage patterns, and child-robot engagement. This information is currently under analysis and will be shared with the scientific community in follow-up papers.

A potential continuation of this work should expand the dialogue features, both in terms of domain coverage and dialogue management capabilities. In order to do that, the most promising direction would be looking for the right balance between a robust mixed-initiative modular approach, like the one described in this paper, and a flexible and more natural end-to-end Large Language Model.

6. Conclusions

The main contributions of this CRI multi-language study in children’s homes are:

- We show that, even in this challenging scenario, the speech recognition and language understanding layers can perform reliably for all activities in the three languages under study, including the relatively low-resourced Ukrainian. This aligns with Xu and Warschauer [16], who reported a rate of inaccurate intent classifications of only 0.3%-0.7% for interactions with CAs. The worst understanding rates came from inter-activity conversational intents like “help” or “repeat”. Based on our study, we recommend increasing the research focus on these general conversational capabilities and the dialogue management level.
- We have corroborated our own prediction from the first iteration of experiments, setting a hard limit on understanding errors around 10% of interactions for this kind of activities. This limit remained constant even after enlarging the domain (x2 types of activities) and extending from 1 to 3 languages.
- We confirmed the common-sense expectation that user inputs are easier to handle when the robot questions are more directed. The intent understanding scores were very similar, but there were fewer errors and unexpected answers to yes/no questions than to multiple-choice ones, which in turn worked better than open-ended ones. More importantly, we were able to quantify this difference and checked that those figures were very similar across all 3 languages.
- We showed how providing mixed-initiative dialogue capabilities is very beneficial for the user experience. When the users must discover the activities by themselves (first iteration), there is a shift from mostly system-driven interactions in the first days to mostly user-driven by the end of the experiment. When the users are explained all the activities before starting the experiment (as in the second

- iteration), both system- and user-driven interactions are observed since day 1.
- We analysed some common dialogue patterns and concluded that “help” and “repeat” functionalities require explicit training of the user. This observation was confirmed in the second iteration of the experiments, where researchers explained the availability of these patterns to the users, who applied it several times. In contrast, the users in the first iteration of the experiment did not get any explanation and those patterns were hardly used.

In addition to these insights, we share a number of statistics about turn-taking, dialogue duration, fallback handling, and error analysis that could be helpful for future systems design.

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